

Evaluate the Effectiveness of Self-Instructional Module (SIM) on knowledge regarding the child safety among the parents of under five children in selected Pre-Schools at Bengaluru

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Abstract: Children are viewed as the foundation of a powerful country. Even though they are so young, children have the power to positively impact the country. Given that the future of the nation rests with them, they are the responsible citizens of the future.

Objectives: The objectives of the study are to determine the relationship between the socio-demographic characteristics of parents of children under five and the Pre-Test knowledge scores, as well as to gauge the effectiveness of the Self Instructional Module (SIM) in raising the knowledge of child safety among parents of children under five.

Methodology: Pre- and post-test research design was the method chosen for this investigation. A handy sampling strategy known as non-probability was modified to choose the samples for the proposed investigation. A sample of 50 was chosen from every parent. The same questionnaire used for the pre-test was utilized for the post-test, which was given seven days following the self-instruction module that preceded the pre-test. The investigator in this study employed a structured knowledge questionnaire to gauge parents' awareness of child safety issues for children under five.

Result: According to the computed t value, which was ($t=2.05$) substantially higher than the table value ($t=1.68$) at the 0.05 level of significance, the study found that there was a significant difference between the post-test knowledge score of parents on child safety.

Conclusion: The study's conclusions demonstrated that SIM was successful in raising parents' awareness of child safety.

Keywords: child safety, self-instructional module, pre-school, Pre-school.

I. INTRODUCTION

Children are viewed as the foundation of a powerful country. Even though they are so young, children have the power to positively impact the country. Given that the future of the nation rests with them, they are the responsible citizens of the future. Since children are tomorrow's leaders, parents, teachers, and other family members must treat them with respect, provide them with extra care, and keep them safe. In addition to receiving a decent, high-quality education, children should also have access to wholesome food, clean clothing, safety, and a healthy living environment where they may feel comfortable at home, at school, and elsewhere. Our children's growth in the future depends on them being in excellent health now. For babies and early toddlers, who love to explore but are oblivious to the risks, a house may be an exciting environment. There are risks in life; youngsters are more likely to be involved in domestic mishaps.

Millions of youngsters suffer lasting disabilities or disfigurements as a result of accidents every year. Domestic accidents were reported to be one of the main causes of mortality in Iraq for children under the age of five. WHO (2001) estimates that accidental incidents claimed the lives of 6,85,000 children under the age of five, the most being traffic accidents, drownings, burns, falls, and poisoning. The world's greatest rate of falls and drowning deaths occurs in children under five.

Therefore, parents need to be aware of the kid safety knowledge technique. The ways in which parents care for their children differ depending on their educational background, experience level, and familiarity with evidence-based practice.

Problem statement

“A study to evaluate the effectiveness of Self-Instructional Module (SIM) on knowledge regarding the child safety among the parents of under five children in selected pre-schools at Bengaluru”

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the knowledge on child safety among parents of under five children
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of Self Instructional Module (SIM) regarding knowledge on child safety among parents of under five children
3. To find the association between the Pre-Test knowledge scores and socio-demographic variables of parents of under five children

Hypothesis

- H₁: The mean post test knowledge scores of parents regarding child safety will be higher than the mean pre test knowledge scores after exposing to Self instructional module at 0.05 level of significance.
- H₂: There will be significant association between pre test levels of knowledge of parents regarding child safety and their selected personal variables at 0.05 level of significance.

II. FIGURES GRAPHS AND TABLES

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON AGE

N=50

Characteristics	Category	Respondents	
		Number	%
Age	20-24 years	4	8%
	25-29 years	30	60%
	30-34 years	14	28%
	35 years and above	2	4%

Table 1 shows that majority of from 30 (30%) are 25-29, 14(28%) are 30-34 ,4(8%) are 20-24 and 2(4%) are above 35 years of age group.

Figure 1: diagram showing percentage of distribution of respondents according to age.

TABLE 2: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON Gender

N=50

Characteristics	Category	Respondents	
		Number	%
Gender	Male	10	20%
	Female	40	80%

Table 2 shows that majority of from 40 (80%) are Female, 10(20%) are male of gender group.

Figure 2 Percentage of parents according to their Gender

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON RELIGION

N=50

Characteristics	Category	Respondents	
		Number	%
RELIGION	Hindu	16	32%
	Muslim	10	20%
	Christianity	20	40%
	Others	04	8%

Table 3 shows that majority of from 20 (40%) are Christinity, 16(32%) are hindu ,10(20%) are muslim and 4(8%) are other religion group.

Figure 3: Percentage of parents according to their religion

TABLE 4: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON EDUCATIONAL STATUS

N=50

Characteristics	Category	Respondents	
		Number	%
EDUCATIONAL STATUS	No formal education	0	0%
	Primary &Secondary	3	06%
	PUC	5	10%
	Degree and above	42	84%

Table 4 shows that majority of from 42 (84%) are degree and above, 5(10%) are puc ,3(06%) are primary and secondary and 0(0%) are no formal education group.

Figure 4: Percentage of parents according to their educational status

TABLE 5: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON TYPE OF FAMILY

N=50

Characteristics	Category	Respondents	
		Number	%
TYPE OF FAMILY	Nuclear	16	32%
	Joint	24	48%
	Extended	10	20%

Table 5 shows that majority of from 24 (48%) are joint family, 16(32%) are nuclear ,10(20%) are extended family group.

Figure 5: Percentage of parents according to their type of family

TABLE 6: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON NUMBER OF CHILDREN

N=50

Characteristics	Category	Respondents	
		Number	%
NUMBER OF CHILDREN	One	12	24%
	Two	18	36%
	Three	10	20%
	Four and above	10	20%

Table 6 shows that majority of from 18(36%) are two children, 12(24%) are one ,10(20%) , four and above 10(20) are number of children.

Figure 6: Percentage of parents according to their number of children

III. DISCUSSION

Although present study discussion is focused with the objectives of the study to assess the “Evaluate the effectiveness of self-instructional module (sim) on knowledge regarding the child safety among the parents of under five children in selected pre-schools at bengaluru”

Methodology

The Imogene King Goal Attainment Model (1971) serves as the foundation for the conceptual framework of this research. A pre-experimental, one-group pretest-post-test design was used to gauge parents' awareness of child safety. A systematic knowledge questionnaire with an emphasis on child protection was created. In conjunction with professional advice and insightful suggestions, the content validity was confirmed. The tool's dependability was evaluated and confirmed. 50 parents of preschool-aged children in Bangalore were chosen for the study using a suitable non-probability selection approach. The collected data were subjected to both inferential and descriptive statistical analysis.

Description of the tool

In the present study the following tool was used.

Part-I: Consisted of 6 items related to socio demographic data of the subjects such as age in years, gender, religion, type of family, educational status and type of family on child safety.

Part-II: Structured knowledge questionnaire consisted of 30 items on knowledge regarding child safety. This divided into 4 aspects

Section A – deals with the item on child safety- 5 items

Section B –deals with the item on child accidents-12 items

Section C –deals with the item on management of accidents-8 items

Section D –deals with the item on prevention of accidents-5 items

Every schedule item contains one right response and three incorrect answers; the knowledge questionnaire has a total score of thirty. A correct answer is worth one mark, while a bad answer is worth zero.

If an instrument measures what it is intended to measure with accuracy, it is said to be valid. When an instrument is legitimate, it accurately captures the idea that it is meant to quantify. Six experts—five of whom are specialists in child health nursing and one of whom is a statistician—were given the tool to test its content validity. Thirty questions make up the final questionnaire.

Results

For religion, family type, number of children, and family income, the computed Chi-square value for the association between parents' pre-test level of knowledge regarding child safety is found to be statistically significant at 0.05 levels. However, it is not found to be statistically significant for age, gender, educational status, or prior knowledge. The results therefore suggest that parents' pretest level of awareness about child safety is highly correlated with their personal factors, such as religion, family type, number of children, and wealth, and they partially support hypothesis H2.

Table 7: Median, Mode, standard deviation and range Pre-test and Post-test knowledge scores of parents regarding child safety.

n =50

Section	Mean	Mean %	Median	Mode	SD	Range	Percentage
Pre test	9.82	32.73	9.5	6	3.89	14	32.73
Post test	25.06	83.53	25.5	27	2.76	11	83.53

Table 7 shows parents' pre- and post-test knowledge scores on child safety. Parent knowledge scores on average were 9.82 in the pre-test, with a mean percentage of 32.73, a median of 9.5, a mode of 6.89, a standard deviation of 3.89, and a range of 14. In the post-test, parents' mean scores were 25.06, a mean percentage of 83.53, a median of 25.5, a mode of 27, a standard deviation of 2.76, and a range of 11.

Table 8: Mean, mean difference, standard deviation of difference, standard error of difference and ‘t’ value of pre-test and post-test knowledge scores parents regarding child safety.

N = 50

Knowledge score	Mean	Mean difference	SD difference	SE	Paired ‘t’ test	Significance
Pre test	9.82					
Post test	25.06	15.24	1.13	0.67	22.92	S

$t_{(49)} = 2.05, (p < 0.05), S = \text{Significant}$

The pre-test and post-test means, according to the data in Table 8, are 9.82 and 25.06, respectively. With a standard deviation difference of ± 1.13 , the mean difference in knowledge scores is 15.24. This suggests that parents' awareness scores about child protection are rising. The significance of the knowledge increase was determined using a Paired 't' test, and the resultant value of $t(50) = 22.92$ was deemed significant at the $p < 0.05$ level. As a result, hypothesis H1 is validated. This suggests that the parents who completed the self-instructional module on child safety have considerably increased their knowledge, and that the improvement in knowledge is not coincidental.

Table 9: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to level of knowledge regarding child safety among parents

N=50

Level of knowledge					
Pre test			Post test		
Poor f(%)	Moderate f(%)	Good f(%)	Poor f(%)	Moderate f(%)	Good f(%)
16(32%)	26(52%)	8(16%)	0(0%)	5(10%)	45(90%)

The frequency and percentage distribution of respondents' knowledge on child safety are shown in Table 9. The degree of knowledge of the maximum 26 (52%) responders in the pre-test was moderate. Eight (16%) had the best knowledge, while 16 (32%) had the worst. On the other hand, all respondents demonstrated a high degree of knowledge in the post-test, suggesting the effectiveness of the SIM.

Results show the association between sociodemographic traits and pretest knowledge of child safety for children under five in early childhood education. At the 0.05 level of significance, the results in Table 3 show a significant connection between each demographic variable. Thus, the H1 hypothesis was approved.

Discussion

- The subjects' total posttest knowledge scores on child safety under five in pre-school exceeded the samples' total pre-test knowledge scores.
- The SIM on child safety under five in preschool has demonstrated a noteworthy increase in the knowledge score, demonstrating the efficacy of the planned educational program.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study SIM on child safety under five years in preschool was effective in enhancing samples knowledge. Pre-test knowledge scores of samples showed a substantial correlation with a variety of demographic characteristics, including age, gender, religion, educational attainment, family type, number of children, income, prior knowledge, and information source. These results suggested that parents' awareness of child safety was more influenced by these factors. Hence, in order for professionals to maintain current knowledge, they must participate in periodic in-service education. This requirement drives administrators to plan ongoing programs on a regular basis.

Ethical Clearance

Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethical committee.

Source of funding: Self

Conflict of Interest: Nil

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